

Analyzing Menstrual Products And Overcoming The Issues Relevantly

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Abstract

The topic of Menstruation has always remained a taboo in the world, which makes managing menstrual health difficult for women. Reviewing menstrual products on the market and improving their quality and affordability is imperative. Our survey found that sanitary pads are India's most used product, but other options such as menstrual cups and reusable cloth pads should also be considered. Women should also be provided with a supportive environment to discuss their menstrual health and dispel myths and misconceptions. It is also possible to reduce the financial burden of menstruation by introducing initiatives such as free menstrual products and menstrual leave policies. In addition to addressing the social stigma attached to menstruation and women's menstrual health in India, this review also examines approaches to enhance accessibility, affordability, and overall quality of menstrual health care for all women.

Keywords : Menstruation, Products, Stigma, Improved menstrual products, Alternate menstrual products

Introduction

Although menstruation is a natural occurrence that women around the globe go through, it is still considered a taboo subject in several societies. While pads are the most common menstrual product today, there is a rich history of menstrual products that came before them¹. In India, menstrual health is still not discussed enough and there is a strong stigma associated with the process. This review will explore the history of menstruation, the available menstrual products, and the stigma associated with menstruation in India.

Since the early 19th century, menstruation has been a socially and culturally constructed phenomenon. This is evidenced by PJ Adams Hillard's work in the Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences, which explores the history of menstruation and how it has been understood and regulated throughout the centuries². Hillard notes that prior to the 19th century, menstruation was perceived as a natural and necessary process, and was not judged or regulated². In the 19th century, menstruation was increasingly seen as a

problem that needed to be regulated and medically managed. This was due to a shift in the understanding of the body and the rise of medical science. Hillard argues that this shift in attitude has led to a stigmatization of menstruation and the marginalization of women who menstruate. This shift in attitude has had a lasting impact on the way menstruation is viewed and regulated³.

The availability of menstrual products is an important factor in promoting menstrual health and hygiene. According to the study by E. Peberdy, A. Jones, and D. Green, published in *Sustainability* in 2019, access to menstrual products should not be taken for granted⁴. According to the authors' findings, there is insufficient availability of menstrual products in various regions globally, particularly in low-income nations, owing to several reasons such as expenses, cultural stigmas, and inadequate access to healthcare facilities⁴. The authors' conclusion suggests that enhancing menstrual health and hygiene requires heightened attention towards promoting wider distribution of menstrual products, especially in areas where their availability is restricted. They also concluded that education and awareness campaigns should be conducted to increase the understanding of menstrual health and hygiene and to reduce the stigma associated with menstruation. This is especially important to ensure that all individuals, regardless of their economic and social backgrounds, have access to the necessary resources to manage their menstrual health and hygiene⁴.

Menstruation continues to be a topic of taboo and stigma in India, as evidenced by a study conducted by B Joshi and P Swarnakar in 2021⁵. According to their research, menstrual taboos are still pervasive and subject to a great deal of stigma in many parts of India. The authors state that social taboos are rooted in a patriarchal and Brahminical ideology which is deeply embedded in Indian society, and that these beliefs continue to be perpetuated by religious and social customs.⁵ Menstrual taboos are so entrenched that they lead to a range of physical and psychological issues for women, including discrimination, poor self-esteem, and a sense of shame. Furthermore, the societal taboos surrounding menstruation in India can substantially impede women's ability to obtain education, employment, and healthcare services⁵. The authors' final recommendation is to prioritize establishing an environment of open dialogue and acceptance to diminish the stigmatization of menstruation in India. This is essential for the advancement of women's rights and well-being in India⁵.

In India, there is a range of menstrual products available, however due to social and cultural factors, there remains a stigma surrounding menstruation. To address this, it is paramount that efforts are made to educate people on menstrual health and create a culture of inclusivity and acceptance⁶.

Stigma Associated with Menstruation in India

The taboos and stigmas surrounding menstruation are deeply rooted in many cultures and societies around the world. Although menstruation is a natural bodily process experienced by almost 50% of the world's population, in numerous societies, it remains concealed under veils of secrecy and disgrace⁷. In India, the taboo surrounding menstruation has deep roots in ancient myth and religious beliefs and continues to be perpetuated through discrimination and harmful practices⁸.

One particularly egregious example of this discrimination is the belief that food cooked by menstruating women is impure and will lead to negative consequences in the afterlife.⁸ This belief is based on ancient scripture and is still espoused by some religious leaders in India. Consequently, women who are

menstruating may frequently be excluded from performing household chores such as cooking and may even be compelled to sleep separately during their menstrual cycle⁹.

This social exclusion extends to other areas of life as well. In some cultures, menstruating women are not allowed to worship or touch holy objects, effectively denying them their right to practice their faith freely.¹⁰

In extreme cases, girls may be banished to small huts or sheds, where they are vulnerable to the elements and to dangerous animals and may even lose their lives¹¹.

Even the practical aspects of menstruation are affected by these taboos. Women are forced to use rudimentary, washable cloths for menstrual protection, which must be washed secretly in order to avoid being seen by others¹². This fear of being associated with menstrual fluids has resulted in young girls feeling ashamed and embarrassed about their bodies, leading to negative attitudes towards their own menstrual cycles¹¹.

The detrimental effects of the societal stigmatization of menstruation on women's physical and emotional well-being are apparent. This is a form of discrimination and exclusion that can have a lasting impact on women's lives¹³. In order to break down these taboos and end discrimination against menstruating women, it is essential to engage in open and honest dialogue, and to promote education and awareness around this natural biological process. Only then can women be empowered to take control of their own bodies, and to live with dignity and respect¹³.

The taboo against speaking about menstruation is also pervasive. This silence can lead to a lack of knowledge and understanding about the menstrual cycle, which can lead to further discrimination and exclusion. In addition, it can result in limited access to menstrual products, potentially resulting in period poverty¹⁴.

The taboo against men having knowledge about menstruation is also a problem. Men are often excluded from conversations about menstruation, which can lead to a lack of understanding and empathy for women's experiences¹⁵. This can lead to further discrimination and exclusion. In some cultures, girls are expected to be in a separate room, have their own belongings (like their own plates, tumbler etc.) and not touch anything or anyone as they will make them impure. This can lead to feelings of isolation and exclusion and can also lead to a lack of access to education and other opportunities. In some cultures, girls are expected to not go to school after attaining puberty¹⁶. This can lead to a lack of education and opportunities and can also lead to further discrimination and exclusion.¹⁰

Lastly, menstrual product poverty (inadequate availability of menstrual products) and insufficient access to clean and private restrooms for women are significant issues in various regions across the globe. This can lead to further discrimination and exclusion and can also lead to health problems¹⁷. Overall, the taboos and stigmas surrounding menstruation are deeply rooted in many cultures and societies around the world. These taboos can lead to discrimination and exclusion and can also lead to a lack of access to education, opportunities, and menstrual products. It is important to challenge these taboos and stigmas to create a more equitable and inclusive society¹⁸.

Poor Menstrual hygiene

The issue of menstrual hygiene has far-reaching implications for women and girls, particularly in developing countries like India¹⁸. Despite advancements in modern technology and medical care, numerous women still struggle to access suitable menstrual hygiene products and hygienic toilet facilities. For instance, in India, it is estimated that merely 18% of women have access to sanitary products, resulting in the remaining 82% having to resort to unhygienic alternatives like cloth rags, sand, ash, or even old newspapers. The use of such materials poses a significant risk to women's health, potentially leading to life-threatening infections like sepsis¹⁹.

Additionally, the insufficient availability of clean water and secluded restroom amenities during menstruation has a significant influence on women's education, with millions of girls worldwide compelled to skip school every month²⁰. The absence of menstrual hygiene products and clean toilets further exacerbates the problem, leading to poor menstrual hygiene and illnesses related to poor sanitation, such as urinary tract infections and reproductive illnesses. In India, inadequate menstrual hygiene has been linked to 70% of all reproductive illnesses, underscoring the necessity for increased awareness and availability of menstrual hygiene products²¹.

In addition to the health implications, the inadequacy of menstrual hygiene products also sustains gender discrimination and stigmatization, reinforcing cultural taboos and social marginalization of women and girls while menstruating. The issue of menstrual hygiene is not merely a health concern, but a human rights issue that demands urgent attention from policymakers, healthcare providers, and the wider public²².

Water Aid published a report stating that illnesses caused by the scarcity of clean water, fundamental sanitation, and hygiene led to the death of almost 800,000 women worldwide in a single year, ranking it as the fifth leading cause of death among women after heart disease, stroke, lower respiratory infections, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease²³. Providing menstrual hygiene products, clean water, and secluded restroom amenities during menstruation is a crucial public health and human rights concern that necessitates prompt action to enhance the health, education, and overall wellbeing of women and girls globally²⁴.

Available Menstrual Products

Menstrual products have been an essential part of a woman's monthly cycle for generations. There are several options available, including pads, menstrual cups, discs, tampons, and period underwear. Each product has its own set of pros and cons that should be considered before making a choice²⁵.

Pads are the most used menstrual product and are often the first choice for many women. Pros of pads include being readily available, being easy to use, and providing good coverage for heavy flow days. However, pads can be bulky, uncomfortable to wear, and tend to leak. They can also create a feeling of dampness, leading to discomfort and odor²⁶.

Menstrual cups are another option and are gaining in popularity. Pros of menstrual cups include being environmentally friendly, being reusable, and having the ability to hold more fluid than pads. They are also more comfortable to wear and less likely to leak²⁶. Cons of menstrual cups include being more difficult to use, requiring regular cleaning, and having a learning curve when it comes to insertion and removal. They may also not be suitable for women with certain physical conditions, such as a tilted uterus²⁶.

Discs are a newer option on the market and are similar in design to menstrual cups. Pros of discs include being comfortable to wear, being reusable, and having the ability to hold more fluid than pads²⁷. They are

also easy to insert and remove and do not have a learning curve like menstrual cups²⁶. Cons of discs include being more difficult to find in stores, being more expensive than other options, and having a limited lifespan.

Tampons are another option for women who want to be more active during their period. Pros of tampons include being discreet and easy to wear, being convenient for physical activity, and being readily available²⁶. Drawbacks of tampons involve the potential for toxic shock syndrome, the need for frequent replacements, and the possibility of discomfort while inserting and removing them.²⁸

Period underwear are a newer option that offers an alternative to traditional menstrual products. Pros of period underwear include being comfortable to wear, being leak-proof, and being convenient for everyday use²⁶. They are also environmentally friendly and can be worn overnight. Cons of period underwear include being more expensive than other options, having a limited lifespan, and being less effective for heavy flow days²⁶.

Type	Pros	Cons	References
Menstrual Pads	Readily available. Easy to use. Good coverage for heavy flow days	Bulky and uncomfortable. Tend to leak. Can create a feeling of dampness and odor	14,29
Menstrual Cups	Environmentally friendly. Reusable. Can hold more fluid than pads. Comfortable to wear. Less likely to leak	Difficult to use. Require regular cleaning. Learning curve for insertion and removal. May not be suitable for women with certain physical conditions	16,30
Menstrual Discs	Comfortable to wear. Reusable. Can hold more fluid than pads. Easy to insert and remove	Difficult to find in stores. More expensive than other options. Limited lifespan	31
Tampons	Discreet and easy to wear. Convenient for physical activity. Readily available.	Risk of toxic shock syndrome. Need for frequent changes. Potential for discomfort during insertion and removal	32-34
Period Underwear	Comfortable to wear. Leak-proof. Convenient for everyday use. Environmentally friendly. Can be worn overnight	More expensive than other options. Limited lifespan. Less effective for heavy flow days	35,36

Table 1: Evaluating the pros and cons of the available menstrual products.

Unveiling the Harmful Chemicals Lurking in Pads and Tampons

For many people who menstruate, period care products like pads and tampons are a necessity. However, while these products are designed to make managing menstrual bleeding easier, they may also come with a host of health and environmental concerns³⁵.

A primary concern with regular pads and tampons is their frequent use of synthetic materials such as rayon and polyester, which are not entirely natural. While some products may contain cotton, this is often

conventional cotton that is grown with toxic pesticides. Moreover, these materials are frequently subjected to chlorine bleaching, resulting in the formation of dioxins and furans, which have been linked to cancer, reproductive toxicity, and endocrine disruption³⁷.

Period care products also raise concerns regarding the use of superabsorbent polymers (SAPs), which are usually made from sodium polyacrylate, a synthetic material that is not environmentally friendly. SAPs, which are intended to have a high liquid-holding capacity, may contain plasticizing chemicals like BPA and other bisphenols. In addition, new technology that utilizes nanoscale materials may eliminate SAPs, but some scientists have concerns about the potential health and environmental impacts of these materials³⁷. Conventional period care products may also pose a risk of pesticide residues, as certain pesticides are associated with cancer and potential endocrine disruption. Products made with conventionally grown cotton have been found to contain pesticide residues. Additionally, the use of plastics and plasticizers in these products can contribute to plastic pollution and may also be linked to endocrine disruptions and cancer³⁸. To aid in easier removal, certain tampons are coated with harmful substances like paraffin, polyethylene (a non-biodegradable plastic), and polyethylene glycol (which may have contamination concerns). In addition, scented options for pads and tampons are available, which may contain unlisted fragrance components that can potentially cause cancer, allergies, and endocrine disruption^{32,33}.

Given the potential health and environmental concerns associated with conventional period care products, many people are turning to alternative options like reusable menstrual cups or cloth pads. These products may be more sustainable and environmentally friendly and can be a safer and healthier choice for those who are concerned about the potential risks associated with conventional period care products³⁹.

Overall, it's important for individuals to be informed about the potential risks associated with the use of conventional period care products, and to make choices that align with their values and concerns. By choosing more sustainable and safer options, individuals can help promote both their own health and the health of the planet¹³.

Breaking the Taboo: Insights on Menstrual Health, Sustainability, and Myths surrounding Menstrual Cups and Pads from a Survey

For many years, menstrual health and hygiene have been a pressing concern in numerous regions globally, particularly in countries with low to middle income levels. In these regions, lack of awareness, social stigma, and limited access to menstrual products and facilities have been identified as some of the major barriers to menstrual hygiene management. In developed countries as well, the quality and environmental impact of menstrual products have come under scrutiny in recent times, despite their comparatively advanced state of menstrual health and hygiene⁴⁰.

In a survey conducted by us on menstrual health and the menstrual products used, it was found that most of the respondents were females between the ages of 15 to 25. Almost 91 percent of them reported using menstrual pads, with only 3.4 percent using menstrual cups⁴¹. The reason for the high usage of pads was attributed to their ease of use and availability. However, a significant number of respondents expressed a desire to switch to other menstrual products, particularly menstrual cups, as they are more sustainable⁴.

The survey revealed that despite the increasing interest in menstrual cups, there are still several barriers that prevent women from using them. One of the most common concerns is the fear of hymen rupture, which is often associated with virginity. This fear is often perpetuated by family members, who may discourage the use of menstrual cups or tampons. However, there is no scientific evidence to support the claim that using menstrual cups or tampons can cause hymen rupture. This highlights the urgent need to create awareness and dispel such myths that prevent women from making an informed choice about menstrual products.

The fear of insertion is another obstacle to the acceptance of menstrual cups. Women may be reluctant to use them due to concerns about the discomfort or pain that may be associated with inserting them. However, research has shown that with proper guidance and instruction, most women can successfully use menstrual cups without discomfort or pain¹⁶.

Respondents also expressed concern about the impact of menstrual products on the environment. The majority felt that menstrual pads could be made more sustainable and environmentally friendly, with the use of organic materials instead of plastics. Additionally, there was a demand for fragrance-free products to avoid potential health issues, and for longer or larger wings in pads to prevent leaks.

The survey also revealed that women wanted fragrance-free products as the menstrual products containing fragrances and other additives can cause irritation and allergic reactions. The Journal of Women's Health published a study stating that the presence of certain chemicals in menstrual products can cause irritation and allergic reactions, ultimately leading to discomfort and pain for some women during menstruation⁴³.

This need for environmentally sustainable menstrual products is supported by research that shows that menstrual products are a significant source of plastic waste, ending up in landfills or oceans. According to a research article published in the Royal Society Open Science, an average woman uses approximately 11,000 disposable menstrual products during her lifetime, leading to a substantial amount of non-biodegradable waste⁴².

More sustainable options for menstrual products, like reusable cloth pads and menstrual cups, exist as alternatives to disposable options. While reusable cloth pads have been available for some time, they are not very convenient for some users due to their bulkiness and difficulty in cleaning. One potential solution could be the development of more compact and easily washable reusable pads that can be easily integrated into a user's routine.

Apart from worries about sustainability, there is an increasing concern about the chemicals employed in the manufacturing process of menstrual products and their potential effect on health. Some studies have found that certain chemicals used in menstrual products, such as dioxins and phthalates, can have adverse effects on reproductive health and hormone balance.

Figure 1: Gender Distribution of Survey Participants.

Figure 2: Age Distribution of the Survey Participants

Figure 3: Distribution of Menstrual Product Usage Among Survey Respondents.

Figure 4: Reasons for Menstrual Product Usage Among Survey Respondents.

Figure 5: Willingness to Try New Menstrual Products Among Survey Respondents.

New Menstrual Products available in the world

In recent years, there has been a growing demand for more sustainable and eco-friendly menstrual products. As a result, several new menstrual products have been developed and are now available in the market. These new menstrual products offer women more choices for managing their periods, with a focus on sustainability, convenience, and comfort⁴¹.

One of the most popular new menstrual products is the menstrual cup, which has gained popularity in recent years. Medical-grade silicone or other pliable materials are used to create menstrual cups, which are inserted into the vagina to collect menstrual blood. Menstrual cups are reusable, making them a more sustainable alternative to disposable pads and tampons. They can also be worn for up to 12 hours at a time, making them more convenient for women who have busy schedules. According to a study published in the *Journal of Women's Health*, menstrual cups were found to be a safe and efficient substitute for disposable menstrual products, and users reported a high level of satisfaction⁴².

Another new menstrual product that has gained popularity in recent years is period underwear. Period underwear is designed to be worn alone or in combination with other menstrual products and is made of absorbent fabric that can hold menstrual blood. This makes period underwear a more sustainable and eco-friendly option, as they can be washed and reused. *BMC Women's Health* published a study which discovered that period underwear is a comfortable and convenient choice for women seeking an alternative to pads and tampons⁴³.

Menstrual discs are another new menstrual product that has been gaining popularity in recent years. Menstrual discs are like menstrual cups, but are flat and disc-shaped, making them more discreet and comfortable for some women. Menstrual discs can also be worn during sexual activity, making them a popular choice for women who want to have sex during their period. A study published in the *Journal of Women's Health* found that menstrual discs are a safe and effective alternative to disposable menstrual products, with a high level of user satisfaction⁴².

In addition to these new menstrual products, there are also a variety of reusable cloth pads available. These pads are made of soft, absorbent fabric and can be washed and reused, making them a more sustainable option than disposable pads. Reusable cloth pads are also a good choice for women who have sensitive skin, as they are made without the harsh chemicals found in disposable pads. The *Journal of Obstetrics and*

Gynecology Canada published a study indicating that reusable cloth pads are a reliable and secure substitute for disposable pads¹⁴.

Overall, the development of new menstrual products has been a positive trend for women, offering more choices and alternatives for managing periods. These products offer sustainability, convenience, and comfort, and are becoming more widely available in the market. However, it is important for women to do their research and choose menstrual products that are safe and healthy, and to speak with their healthcare provider if they have any concerns about using new menstrual products.

Product Type	Improvement that can be done	References
Menstrual Pads	Thinner, more absorbent materials. Wings for better leak protection. Organic and eco-friendly options. Improved adhesive technology to prevent shifting.	14,29,31
Menstrual Cups	More comfortable. Flexible materials. Wider range of sizes. Collapsible and travel-friendly designs. Pull tabs for easier removal	4,16,30,31,37,44
Menstrual Tampons	Applicators made of sustainable materials, organic and non-toxic options. Customizable absorbency. Introduction of applicators for easier insertion. Expansion of product lines to include sport tampons, compact tampons, and more sustainable options	28,32,34,45,46
Menstrual Discs	More comfortable, flexible designs. Less mess during removal. Less risk of toxic shock syndrome. Introduction of disposable, single-use options for convenience. Increase in size and capacity for longer wear time. Use of flexible, comfortable materials for better fit. Development of reusable, eco-friendly options	13,25
Period Panties	More absorbent and leak-proof materials. Wider range of sizes and styles. Eco-friendly and sustainable options. Use of moisture-wicking, breathable materials for comfort. Expansion of size range to accommodate different body types and menstrual flow levels	25,43,47

Table 2: Improvements that can be done to the existing menstrual products.

Eco-friendly napkins

New eco-friendly pads are a revolutionary solution that provides a more sustainable and biodegradable menstrual product option for women. Traditional pads are often made with synthetic materials that are not environmentally friendly, leading to a significant impact on the environment. In response to this problem, eco-friendly pads are made of natural and organic materials that reduce waste and support a more sustainable menstrual cycle⁴⁸.

Eco-friendly pads are made from organic materials like cotton, bamboo, and corn starch. The use of natural materials in the production of eco-friendly pads reduces the environmental impact that comes with the use of synthetic materials⁴⁹. These pads do not contain bleach, plastics, or other harmful chemicals, which is a significant benefit for the environment as well as for women's health. In addition, these pads are biodegradable, meaning they can be decomposed by natural processes without causing any harm to the environment⁴⁹.

One of the main benefits of eco-friendly pads is their environmental sustainability. As mentioned, traditional pads take a long time to decompose, and the chemicals used in them can cause damage to the environment. Eco-friendly pads, on the other hand, are environmentally safe and reduce waste. The natural materials used in these pads are also less likely to cause skin irritation or allergic reactions, which is a common problem with traditional pads⁴⁸. Another benefit of eco-friendly pads is their affordability. Although there may be some variation depending on the brand and the retailer, eco-friendly pads are often available at a similar or lower price than traditional pads. This can make them a more accessible and cost-effective option for women^{48,49}.

However, there are some limitations to eco-friendly pads. For example, they may not be as widely available in stores as traditional pads. This can make it difficult for women to find the right product when they need it. Additionally, some women may not find these pads to be as comfortable or absorbent as traditional pads. It is essential to note that there may be some variation in the quality of eco-friendly pads depending on the brand and the specific product⁴⁸.

The new eco-friendly pads are a promising solution to the environmental problems posed by traditional menstrual products. They are made from natural and organic materials, are environmentally safe, and are affordable⁴⁸. However, there may be some limitations regarding availability, quality, and absorbency. Women who are interested in reducing their environmental footprint and supporting more sustainable menstrual cycles may find eco-friendly pads to be a great alternative to traditional pads⁴⁹.

Free Menstrual products

Millions of women and girls worldwide are impacted by period poverty, which refers to the inability to access menstrual products due to financial limitations. In many countries, menstrual products are taxed as luxury items, making them unaffordable for those living in poverty. This has led to an ongoing movement to make menstrual products more accessible, including proposals to make them available for free. In India, where millions of women and girls live in poverty, access to menstrual products is often limited. Inadequate access to menstrual products may lead to substandard menstrual hygiene and health, which in turn can result in infections and other health complications. Therefore, providing menstrual products for free can be a crucial step towards ensuring menstrual hygiene for all women and girls⁴⁸.

The idea of providing free menstrual products has gained traction in recent years, with several governments and organizations implementing such programs. Scotland became the first country to offer free menstrual

products in 2020, with the Scottish government allocating £8.7 million to fund the program. In the United States, several cities and states have also started providing free menstrual products in schools and public facilities, including New York City, California, and Illinois⁴⁹.

Offering free menstrual products can have a substantial effect on the lives of those who are unable to afford them. It can help to reduce absenteeism in schools and workplaces, as girls and women will no longer have to miss school or work due to their periods. It can also improve the overall health and wellbeing of individuals, as they will no longer have to resort to using unsafe alternatives like rags or toilet paper. Moreover, free menstrual products can help to reduce the stigma around menstruation, as it sends a message that periods are a natural and normal part of life, and not something to be ashamed of^{49,50}.

In India, the government has made efforts to address this issue. The government has launched the Menstrual Hygiene Scheme, which provides free sanitary pads to girls in government schools. The scheme also provides funding for the installation of sanitary pad vending machines in schools and public places. Moreover, several non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in India are striving to provide menstrual products to girls and women who require them. One such organization is Goonj, which collects and distributes menstrual products in rural areas of the country^{48,51}.

One argument against free menstrual products is the cost. However, the cost of providing free menstrual products is relatively low, especially when compared to the cost of other public health programs. In Scotland, for example, the cost of providing free menstrual products in schools was estimated at just over £8 million per year, while the cost of the NHS in Scotland was over £14 billion in 2020. Moreover, the cost of providing free menstrual products can be offset by the benefits that it provides, including improved health and productivity, as well as reduced absenteeism.

Another argument against free menstrual products is that it may encourage dependency. However, research suggests that providing free menstrual products does not encourage dependency, but rather helps to alleviate financial stress and improve access to education and work. Moreover, free menstrual products can be provided in conjunction with education and awareness programs, which can help to promote self-sufficiency and improve overall health and wellbeing^{48,52}.

To sum up, offering free menstrual products can greatly benefit those who cannot afford them by enhancing health and productivity, reducing absenteeism, and combating stigma related to menstruation. While there may be concerns around cost and dependency, the benefits of providing free menstrual products outweigh the costs and can be provided in conjunction with education and awareness programs. It is important to continue to promote access to menstrual products for all, and work towards ending period poverty.

Figure 6: Attitudes Toward Free Menstrual Products Among Survey Respondents.

Menstrual Leave for women

Menstrual leave, also known as period leave, is a policy that allows female employees to take time off from work during their menstrual cycle. This concept has been gaining momentum in recent years, as more and more countries and companies have started implementing it. In this essay, we will explore the concept of menstrual leave, its benefits and challenges, and its implementation in India and around the world, with citations to relevant studies and reports^{53,54}.

Firstly, the benefits of menstrual leave are manifold. Menstruation is a natural process and affects most women every month. However, it is also a source of physical discomfort, pain, and sometimes even emotional distress. Women often need to take painkillers or use heating pads to manage menstrual cramps. Moreover, menstrual flow can be heavy, leading to a sense of unease and even embarrassment. Menstrual leave can help women manage these issues better, as they can take time off from work to rest and take care of themselves^{55,56}.

Menstrual leave refers to a type of paid or unpaid leave that is available to women who are experiencing menstrual cramps, heavy bleeding, or other related symptoms. This type of leave is meant to help women manage their symptoms and take time off work when necessary. Several countries, such as Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, and Indonesia, have made menstrual leave a standard workplace policy^{55,57}.

Furthermore, menstrual leave can be seen as a step towards gender equality in the workplace. Menstruation is a female-specific issue and is often stigmatized and misunderstood. By acknowledging and providing support for menstrual health, organizations can signal their commitment to gender equality and to creating a more inclusive and supportive work culture. It can also be seen to break down barriers to women's professional advancement, as they can take time off without worrying about the negative consequences on their careers^{58,59}.

However, there are also challenges associated with menstrual leave. One concern is that menstrual leave could reinforce gender stereotypes and discrimination. If women are seen as "weak" or "incapable" during their periods, it could perpetuate the idea that they are less productive or reliable than men. Moreover, if menstrual leave is not provided as a standard benefit but rather an optional policy, it could lead to further discrimination against women who choose to take it^{60,61}.

To address these concerns, some advocates of menstrual leave have proposed a more flexible approach, such as allowing women to take sick leave or personal days as needed, rather than specifically designating

menstrual leave. By implementing this approach, women could take time off from work for menstrual symptoms without encountering discrimination or stigma^{54,60}.

Despite these challenges, menstrual leave is gaining popularity in India and around the world. In India, some states have already implemented menstrual leave policies. For example, in 2017, the state of Bihar announced that it would provide two days of paid menstrual leave every month to female government employees. Following this, in 2018, the state of Maharashtra also began to offer one to two days of paid menstrual leave each month. These policies have been praised for their potential to improve female employees' health and wellbeing⁶².

Elsewhere in the world, menstrual leave policies are being considered or implemented in several countries. For instance, in 2019, the Australian state of Victoria passed a law allowing for paid menstrual and menopause leave. In Japan, some companies have been providing menstrual leave since the early 20th century, although it is still not a widespread practice. In the UK, a recent survey found that nearly two-thirds of women believe that menstrual leave would be beneficial, although no formal policies have been introduced yet⁵⁵.

In conclusion, menstrual leave is a concept that is gaining momentum in India and around the world. While there are challenges associated with it, such as the potential for reinforcing gender stereotypes, menstrual leave can also be seen as a way to improve female employees' health and wellbeing and to promote gender equality in the workplace. While organizations and governments consider adopting this policy, it is crucial to bear in mind the potential advantages and challenges, and to implement it in a manner that is fair and inclusive for all employees, irrespective of their gender^{56,60}.

Figure 7: Attitudes Toward Menstrual Leave Among Survey Respondents.

Conclusion

This review paper explored the idea of improving the quality of menstrual products and analyzed the advantages and disadvantages of different options available. We also shed light on the stigma associated with menstruation in India and the struggles faced by women due to lack of education, awareness, and hygiene. While menstrual pads are the most used product, they have their own set of disadvantages, such as being non-eco-friendly and containing potentially harmful additives. As a solution, eco-friendly napkins made from plant fibers have been suggested as a viable alternative. While menstrual cups are sustainable, there is a mental block and stigma attached to them, making them less popular among women. This review

also highlights the importance of providing free menstrual products as a necessity and the need for menstrual leave for women in the workplace. With further research and development, it is possible to improve the quality of menstrual products and make them more accessible and eco-friendlier, while also tackling the social stigma associated with menstruation.

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